

Impact of Guerilla Marketing on Millennials Purchase Intention

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ABSTRACT

The study identifies and determines the factors of guerrilla marketing having an influence on millennials purchase intention. Primary data was collected from 176 respondents from Mangalore city, Karnataka State. SmartPLS 3.0 was used for statistical analysis. Measurement Model, factor analysis and SEM model were analyzed to examine the impact. The study highlights the contributing factors to millennials purchase intention due to guerrilla advertising technique.

Keywords: Millennials, Guerrilla Advertising, Creativity, Surprise, Clarity, Novelty, Aesthetics, Relevance, Humor, Emotional Arousal, Purchase Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION :

In 1984, an American author by the name of Jay Conrad Levinson published the first edition of "Guerrilla Marketing." In his eyes, this is a novel approach to achieving common objectives, a tried-and-true strategy for making the most money possible while spending the least. It is a struggle to gain control of the thought processes of the consumer (Behal & Sareen, 2014) [1]. Guerrilla marketing was first developed for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) since it assists these businesses in demoralizing their competitors via the use of modest, periodic, and unexpected assaults, necessitating quick response while also demanding the use of ingenuity and inventiveness. In an aggressive marketing technique known as guerrilla marketing, millennials are reached via a number of channels by combining public relations, advertising, and marketing tactics. A guerilla marketer may choose from eye-catching street visuals, odd happenings, noteworthy events, buzz, and product placement. The goal of media planning is to ensure that a certain amount of money is spent in the most efficient manner possible by targeting the ideal audience at the ideal frequency and with the smallest amount of waste. Guerrilla communication operates similarly. Not just medium-to-small businesses but even large corporations are finding that guerilla marketing is appealing and are beginning to use it at various phases of their strategic planning. Guerrilla marketing thrives at an era of fast technological change in millennials behavior, as seen by the growing number of young people who no longer watch television. Due to the enormous amount of promotional material that can be found online, online advertising has become the form with the most rapid growth. However, this leads to difficulties with advertising clutter, which in turn affects consumer attention to promotional messages, impacts adversely on consumer attitude towards the commercials, and diminishes memorability of both the ad and the brand that is being pushed. Additionally, audiences themselves are more literate as a result of excessive advertising exposure. They are able to decipher complicated pictures with just a few hints. During that time period, increased literacy in turn leads to distrust, which in turn leads to unfavorable views toward the message. Guerrilla marketing has thus replaced conventional marketing methods, which are no longer as successful as they once were in today's market. Even while traditional marketing may not be totally replaced by guerrilla marketing, it does, without a doubt, indicate new avenues, supports the tried-and-true marketing methods, and supplements them with unorthodox aspects, all with the goal of achieving advertising effectiveness and influencing millennials behavior (Yüksekbilgili, 2014) [2]. The study considers millennials who are born from 1981 to 1996, as they are more dynamic in nature and are highly influenced to purchased based on attractive visual ads.

2. RELATED WORKS :

Guerrilla marketing has several meanings, but its fundamental ideas are based on the unorthodox approaches and settings that make it possible to hit the appropriate clients at the right moments in a unique yet relevant manner, leaving a lasting and memorable impression. The results of this research integrate into the model the impacts of guerrilla marketing as well as the medium through which it operates, guerilla advertising.

Table 1: Related works on Guerrilla Marketing

S. No	Focus	Outcome	Reference
1.	Novelty	Traditional marketing demands certain financial resources, but guerilla marketing mostly invests time, energy, inspiration, and expertise. The ability of a company to set itself apart from its competitors and its effectiveness in reaching those prospective consumers are crucial in guerilla marketing. In order to succeed in this goal, guerilla tactics need to be fresh and make an impact. It's customary to use the term "novelty" to describe creativity, which is characterized by two traits: deviation from the norm and a feeling of singularity (originality). When determining whether a product is innovative or not, a number of studies believe that novelty should be the primary consideration. In the field of advertising, a new commercial is one that cannot be compared to similar campaigns for the same product category. According to the findings of the study, novelty is defined as "the perceived uniqueness of a product, "its distinctive and unconventional nature," and "having an extraordinarily high positive valence for the customer".	Tam & Khuong (2015). [3]; Nunthiphatprueksa (2017). [4]
2	Surprise	In sensation and ambient marketing and, the two sub-components of guerilla marketing, surprise is a sensational experience, a potent aspect that makes the consumers "wow" or "aha". A person who is astonished will stop what they are doing and pay attention to what has shocked them. Guerilla marketing makes use of this idea to break through the clutter of advertising and capture the attention of consumers that surprise becomes the main of the guerrilla marketing ideology. When compared to the massive funds that huge corporations may devote to mainstream media like television, radio, newspapers, etc., small businesses will find the surprise effect to be an effective alternative. The customers are aroused and digest information in a more complex manner when they are surprised. In other words, inconsistency between an advertisement and what consumers anticipate from it will encourage them to analyse it more thoroughly. If the message that is actually received is different from what was anticipated, consumers will have more positive sentiments about the advertisement and the business, as well as a greater	Yuniarto, et al. (2020). [5]; Damar-Ladkoo (2016). [6]

		desire to make a purchase.	
3	Clarity	The capacity of a person to comprehend the meaning of a communication is related to the concept of message clarity. The cognitive effort required by listeners to grasp a communication increase with its complexity. In order for consumers to take the advertised brand or product into consideration, they must initially comprehend the message of the advertising. Guerrilla tactics are unusual ones. The commercials that were analysed for this research were ones that were shown in peculiar settings and carried out in unanticipated manners. Clear communication of the content is crucial in this study since the respondents will watch the adverts to validate both the planned and perceived impacts.	Milak & Dobrinić, (2017). [7]; Wendland (2016). [8]
4	Aesthetics	The perceived newness of a product may be measured by indicators such as how stylish it is and how well-crafted it is. In this context, the concept of aesthetics refers not to beauty but rather harmony and the organised building of the message. Aesthetics is the practise of combining different indicators in order to create more intricate interactions. When anything has particular impacts on cognitive reference, such as in this situation, the assessment of guerilla ads, it is vital to bring up the aesthetics element as a component to consider. When it comes to advertising, aesthetically pleasing results may be produced "by purposefully breaching specific constraints of the code, so as to activate overlapping and interweaving semantic chains that are ordinarily not related". The surprising manner in which the characteristics are blended and related in guerilla marketing contributes to the overall well-craftiness of the advertisements.	Anyasor (2022). [9]; Yuniarto (2020). [10]
5	Humor	Customers' attention has to be captured before they become interested in the product, which is also marketers' primary objective. It is for this reason why ads, in particular, often use humorous elements. Additionally, it is said that humorous advertising improves buy intent and promote a more favorable attitude toward the ads and businesses. However, different academics have come up with quite different ways of constructing humor. Humor is defined in terms of the "stimulus attributes", and it will be decided via the usage of comedy devices. Humor devices may be thought of as the style or method of humor that is employed to make an advertising "humorous". As the context of exposure to commercials differ in the study as compared to the original areas where the advertisements were put, what will be certainly assessed is the stimulus qualities of the comedy in the advertisements instead of advertisements themselves. The purpose of the study is not to conduct an in-depth investigation of these theories or devices; rather, it	Othman, H. (2020). [11]; Wiryawan & Wardana (2020). [12]

		seeks to measure the perceived level of humor. At the same time, it is important to note that this evaluation will take place while simultaneously stressing the fact that because of this difference in context, the perceived level of humor	
6	Relevance	Relevance is a measurement of how information included in an advertisement enhances or undermines its message. There are two aspects to relevance that are reflected in this metric: ad relevance, which refers to how customers feel about the advertising' effectiveness in conveying information about the product, and brand relevance, which indicates how well-known or applicable consumers feel the brand is. Advertising that is unique or unexpectedly startling is not always creative, particularly if the target audience cannot understand its purpose. Consumers will come away from their encounters with certain expectations that are embedded deep inside those experiences. Their perception of novelty in an advertisement depends on how far it deviates from their expectations. However, novelty will not equate to originality if such a unique aspect fails to communicate a specific meaning of the promoted product. Therefore, meaningfulness, also known as relevancy, is an essential component that not only assists the audience in gaining an understanding of the product, but also raises the audience's estimation of the originality and attitude of the advertisement.	Usani, N. E. (2022). [13]; Farooqui, R. (2021). [14]
7	Emotional Arousal	It has been hypothesized that experiencing something new might result in a range of feelings. In turn, these feelings assess whether or not the customer would accept or reject the advertisement. Valance, also known as pleasantness or hedonic values, and arousal, often known as the activity of the body, are the two primary characteristics of an emotion. In spite of this, emotions have been described in a variety of contradictory approaches, which makes it challenging to comprehend their fundamental characteristics and to locate an appropriate rating system with which to assess them. It is described emotions as follows: (a) the experience or conscious sensation of emotion; (b) the processes that occur in the brain and neurological system; and (c) the visible expressive patterns of emotions (particularly on the face). The phrase "collection of changes in body and brain system that react to specific settings of one's perceptions, real or remembered, relevant to a certain item or event" is another frequent description of emotion. According to research, high moods cause people to evaluate unexpected stimuli more favorably, whereas negative moods cause people to evaluate them less favorably. Therefore, the contents of the advertisement that have the potential to stir the emotions will have an influence on the efficacy of the advertising, which	Šramová, B. (2015). [15]; Dinh & Mai (2015). [16]

		will in turn have an impact on the intention to buy.	
8	Information Adaption	Adoption of information is the process through which individuals consciously use information. People are exposed to brand-related with a great deal of information on social media due to adverts. Besides, not all content on social media has the same effect on users; there are differences in the strength of the impact. Individual consumers evaluate the accuracy of information, and they are more likely to embrace it if they believe it to be significant. Adoption of information has been the subject of study in the past, which has shown that it influences consumers' intentions to buy. Nevertheless, the information adoption was offered as an additional brand image predictor in this research study by the authors. The brand image may be changed by the communication doings of organizations; information conveyed via ads is thus deemed crucial for purchase intention.	Gökerik, et al. (2018). [17]; Gkarane (2019). [18]
9	Purchase Intention	The consumer will have certain attitudes about the commercials they see. The stronger the buying intention clients have, which in turn is a crucial criterion to forecast their purchasing behavior, the more innovative and trustworthy the advertisements are. Their propensity to acquire a thing increases with their buying intention. Furthermore, research has shown that premeditated actions might affect follow-through. As a consequence of this, having a grasp of a person's intentions will make it possible to comprehend his actions.	Mahdavi Meymand & Kazemi (2018). [20]; Selan, et al. (2021). [21]; Spahic & Parilti (2019). [22]

3. CONCEPTUAL MODEL :

The study has proposed a model based on systematic review of literature and the variables are adapted from the prior published scholarly articles to measure the influence of the guerilla marketing on Purchase intention. The study identified the exogenous variables as; Creativity (Tam & Khuong, 2015)[3] includes- Novelty (Scherer, 2005)[22]; (Zhang, 1996) [23], Relevance (Zhang, 1996) [23] and Aesthetic (Zhang, 1996) [23], and other variables are Surprise (Zhang, 1996) [23]; (Boulding, et al., 1993) [24], Clarity (De Pelsmacker, et al.,1998).[26], Humor (Boulding, et al., 1993) [24], Emotional Arousal (Dinh & Mai, 2015)[16], Information Adaption (Gökerik, et al., 2018)[17]; (Gkarane, 2019)[18], and endogenous variable Purchase Intention (Brown, 2009)[25]; (De Pelsmacker, et al.,1998)[26]. Below Figure1 exhibits the proposed model for this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for this study

Source: Author

4. OBJECTIVES :

The purpose of this research is to establish the contributing elements of guerrilla marketing and to ascertain how they affect millennials propensity to make purchases after seeing guerilla commercials. This research is anticipated to provide a solid framework for businesses in Mangalore, Karnataka State, based on the idea that guerrilla marketing, particularly guerrilla advertising, the most cutting-edge and inventive aspect of guerrilla marketing, is a well-liked and practical instrument not only for SMEs but also for any firm to produce an efficient and successful approach to their clients.

5. METHODOLOGY :

Secondary data for the study is collected through published scholarly articles from google scholar and primary data is collected from 166 respondents who were millennials from Mangalore City, Karnataka State with the help of well- structured questionnaire. Convenient sampling method was used to collect data. SPSS statistical software is used to analyze the effect of contributing factors of guerilla marketing to purchase intentions. Structural Equation Modelling is developed.

6. ANALYSIS :

6.1 Measurement Model:

The study has reflective model and it is satisfactory as the factor loadings are above 0.700. The reliability and validity of data is established as the Cronbach alpha and composite reliability values are above 0.700 and AVE values are above 0.500 (Table 2). The R-square value is 0.677 which indicates, purchase intention has moderate effect on other latent variables as the value is above 0.50 as suggested by Hair, et al. (2011) (Figure 2). The Q-Square value is 0.467 indicating the model has good predictive relevance.

Table 2: Summary of Measurement Model

Constructs	Indicators	Outer Loadings	Indicator Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Clarity	CR1	0.883	0.779	0.954	0.964	0.844
	CR2	0.944	0.891			

	CR3	0.916	0.839			
	CR4	0.916	0.838			
	CR5	0.935	0.874			
Creativity	CT1	0.873	0.763	0.916	0.935	0.707
	CT2	0.889	0.791			
	CT5	0.869	0.756			
	CT6	0.855	0.731			
	CT7	0.778	0.605			
	CT8	0.773	0.598			
Emotional Arousal	EA1	0.924	0.853	0.960	0.966	0.877
	EA2	0.918	0.843			
	EA3	0.965	0.930			
	EA4	0.939	0.882			
Humor	HM1	0.868	0.753	0.918	0.942	0.803
	HM2	0.914	0.835			
	HM3	0.926	0.858			
	HM4	0.876	0.768			
Information Adoption	IA1	0.772	0.596	0.700	0.766	0.620
	IA3	0.803	0.645			
Purchase Intention	P11	0.890	0.791	0.928	0.944	0.738
	P12	0.914	0.835			
	P13	0.773	0.598			
	P14	0.901	0.812			
	P15	0.757	0.573			
	P16	0.904	0.817			
Surprise	SP1	0.809	0.655	0.922	0.918	0.790
	SP2	0.924	0.854			
	SP3	0.928	0.861			

Source: Field Survey Data

Discriminant Validity is established as per Fornell and Larcker method and Hetrotrait and Monotrait ratio as the values of the square root of AVE is higher than the inter correlation with other constructs (Table 3) and all the values are less than 0.90 (Table 4).

Table 3: Discriminant Validity as per Fornell and Larcker

Constru cts	Clarity	Creativity	Emotional Arousal	Humor	Information Adoption	Purchase Intention	Surprise
Clarity	0.919						
Creativity	0.620	0.841					
Emotiona l Arousal	0.111	0.048	0.937				
Humor	0.698	0.677	0.087	0.896			
Informati on Adoption	0.075	0.031	0.044	0.101	0.788		
Purchase Intention	0.603	0.602	0.065	0.740	0.250	0.859	
Surprise	0.016	0.074	0.027	0.004	0.085	0.036	0.889

Source: Field Survey Data

Table 4: Hetrotrait- Monotrait Ratio

Constructs	Clarity	Creativity	Emotional Arousal	Humor	Information Adoption	Purchase Intention
Clarity						
Creativity	0.660					
Emotional Arousal	0.094	0.054				
Humor	0.745	0.735	0.087			
Information Adoption	0.138	0.139	0.084	0.185		
Purchase Intention	0.624	0.637	0.062	0.775	0.609	
Surprise	0.040	0.055	0.038	0.034	0.195	0.071

Source: Field Survey Data

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Source: Field Survey Data

6.2 Structural Model:

Further the model was analyzed using model fit analysis and the results indicates, SRMR is 0.096, NFI is 0.673 and rms Theta is 0.207, all the values are close to zero, therefore, the model has acceptable fit (Table 5).

Table 5: Results of Model Fit analysis

SRMR	NFI	rms Theta
0.096	0.673	0.207

Source: Field Survey Data

The hypotheses for the study are validated at 95% confidence level with 5% significance level. Below Figure 2 and Table 7 shows structural model and results of hypotheses testing.

Figure 3: Structural Model for the study

Table 6: Results of hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Path	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	Inference
H ₀₁	Creativity -> Purchase Intention	0.129	0.063	2.050**	Supported
H ₀₂	Clarity -> Purchase Intention	0.132	0.071	1.852	Not Supported
H ₀₃	Humor -> Purchase Intention	0.593	0.080	7.451***	Supported
H ₀₄	Emotional Arousal -> Purchase Intention	-0.006	0.044	0.148	Not Supported
H ₀₅	Surprise -> Purchase Intention	-0.001	0.044	0.021	Not Supported
H ₀₆	Information Adoption -> Purchase Intention	0.324	0.066	4.872***	Supported

Note: ***p < .01; **p < .05; *p < .10

Source: Field Survey Data

Hypotheses H₀₁, H₀₃ and H₀₆ is supported showing that creativity, humor and information adoption have a positive on millennials purchase intention as the empirical t-value is above 1.96 at 5% level of significance (Table 6 and Figure 3) whereas H₀₂, H₀₄ and H₀₅ are not supported showing clarity, emotional arousal and surprise does not have positive impact on millennials purchase intentions as their empirical values were less than the required value of 1.96 (Table 6 and Figure 3).

6.3 Importance Performance Map Analysis (IPMA):

“The important – performance matrix analysis (IPMA) also known as important – performance map analysis gives us an idea regarding the relative importance and performance of exogenous constructs in their relationship with endogenous construct” [27][28].

6.3.1 IPMA Construct Wise:

Figure 4: IPMA construct wise

Source: Field Survey Data

When one unit is added to the purchase intention, the performance of it will increase from 34.537 to 35.537. In this study, Creativity and clarity construct require more improvements as they assume moderate values in performance and total effect.

Table 8: IPMA results construct wise

Constructs	Performances	Effect	Total Value
Clarity	30.249	0.131	34.668
Creativity	32.947	0.126	34.663
Emotional Arousal	65.987	-0.007	34.530
Humor	30.572	0.615	35.152
Information Adoption	36.804	0.302	34.839
Surprise	80.854	-0.004	34.533

Source: Field Survey Data

6.3.1 IPMA Indicator wise:

Figure 4: IPMA indicator wise

Source: Field Survey Data

Table 8: IPMA results indicator wise construct wise

Indicators	Performances	Effect	Total Value	Indicators	Performances	Effect	Total Value
CR1	27.162	0.025	30.274	EA2	63.919	-0.001	65.986
CR2	30.811	0.029	30.278	EA3	64.189	-0.001	65.986
CR3	32.432	0.026	30.275	EA4	68.514	-0.002	65.985
CR4	32.568	0.027	30.276	HM1	30.541	0.145	30.717
CR5	28.378	0.031	30.280	HM2	28.243	0.167	30.739
CT1	34.324	0.020	32.967	HM3	30.000	0.179	30.751
CT2	34.324	0.021	32.968	HM4	33.784	0.154	30.726
CT5	31.622	0.022	32.969	IA1	37.162	0.134	36.938
CT6	34.459	0.020	32.967	IA3	36.486	0.151	36.955
CT7	31.757	0.026	32.973	SP1	79.865	0.003	80.857
CT8	31.892	0.025	32.972	SP2	80.405	-0.004	80.850
EA1	64.189	-0.001	65.986	SP3	80.541	-0.003	80.851

Source: Field Survey Data

CR4, CT2 and CT6 assumes highest degree of importance of 32.568, 34.324 and 31.622 respectively with effect of 0.027, 0.021 and 0.022 respectively (Table 8).

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

The reliability and validity are established for the study. The model fit is acceptable (table 5). Creativity positively influences purchases. It is observed that respondents feel that the guerilla advertisements are “fascinating, original, innovative ideas, allow products to be differentiated, provides enjoyment, developed with care and are unique”. Further, if the advertisements are “playful, funny, humorous and amusing”, respondents feel more humorous and therefore, it favorably impacts the millennials purchase intention. Additionally, guerrilla advertisement which provides maximum information with relevant details helps make purchases easier, makes it effective and motivates them to buy more. Therefore, information adoption is influencing purchase intention. However, respondents feel clarity factor needs to be improved. The messages passed by using guerrilla advertisements should be clear and easy to understand. Further, ads should make the viewer feel “aroused, jittery, awake, frenzied). Therefore, emotions should be aroused viewing the ads which makes one connected. Moreover, the ads should bring more surprises and create Startled effect. Even if the surprise element was said to be the foundation of guerrilla marketing and to have a distinguishing impact between guerrilla and conventional marketing, the link between surprise and the dependent variable could not be established with certainty. However, the millennial generation's buying intentions were influenced by humour element. Those users with a high demand for cognition are significantly less impacted by information adoption but are more convinced by message strength than those users with a low need for cognition, which suggests that differences in user characteristics may be to blame for this phenomenon. Clarity of message may be a balance between information adoption and message clarity. Additionally, regular users are more likely to be responsive to humorous and educational appeals. The large age demographic, which spans from 1981 to 1996, contributes directly to these hypotheses in a number of different ways. Culture was another issue to consider when determining how personal motivating values impact the efficacy of funny expression. In addition, in order to discuss the inventiveness of guerilla marketing, it is necessary to point out that customers need to be able to find certain hidden meanings in the promotional materials. Novelty won't inspire innovation without it. Millennials' purchase intentions were most strongly influenced by the combination of the three elements, demonstrating the power of creativity to influence attitudes and actions. When a single exposure may not be enough to change a consumer's attitude toward an advertising or brand, the frequency of commercial exposure is another factor that has to be considered. Although respondents in this research were only exposed to advertising once, the sheer volume of ads they had to look at to get an overall opinion may have resulted in multiple exposures, amplifying the impact of originality on their purchasing decisions. The effect of creativity on relevance did not strengthen the idea that for creativity to be gauged, customers must be able to comprehend the message through its clarity and

significance to the advertisements. The clearness of ads on purchase intention did not support the idea that the clear messages do not mean it communicates a new message but communicate in a new way. The considerable influence of emotion arousal on the dependent variable doesn't support the idea that emotion appeal in ads affects consumers favourably. Furthermore, various people (valence focus and arousal focus) will likewise react differently. Creativity emerged as the factor with the greatest influence on the actions of consumers, according to the findings. To ensure that the freshness and beauty of the message are sent to the audiences, managers should take this issue into account while adopting guerilla methods, particularly when using commercials. It is important to strike a balance between the creative aspect of an advertising and the significance of the information it conveys. This is because consumers need to comprehend an advertisement before they can judge its creative merit. If not, the outcomes can be different. Arousal of emotions also has a significant impact. It demonstrates that the responders must feel something (after they have grasped it), and then their conduct will be influenced by the effect. Managers should be concerned about this since it may not be the amount of information but the sentiments evoked by the messaging that convince consumers to buy. In this light, the channels that may provide these impacts may succeed in their objectives. It's possible that managers may find the model useful. While the majority of the brands in the advertising are well-known and come from large corporations, guerilla marketing is more accurately described by the manner they are executed (they are guerrilla tactics). Given its potent effects, guerilla marketing is becoming an increasingly popular option, as seen by the fact that large corporations are promoting it. The Millennial generation served as the primary focus of this research since they represent the most important and lucrative client demographic not only in Mangalore city but also around the globe.

8. CONCLUSION :

Guerrilla marketing is considered to be relatively new not because it is a new concept but rather because only a limited amount is known about it. However, by including its primary impacts into the most popular marketing strategy, the study discovered a considerable influence of guerrilla marketing on customer purchase intention, greatly supporting prior research and suggestions concerning the use of this kind of marketing. Although it is expected that this form of exploratory study will have limits, the statistical tools helps to fulfill outcomes and ideas in advertising and integrating them into a model of guerrilla marketing for Millennials in Mangalore City. This is despite the fact that limitations are unavoidable in this kind of research. The findings revealed that aspects of advertising such as creativity, humor, and information adoption have a direct and beneficial effect on the millennial generation's propensity to make a purchase.

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